

Title: Data Science Pragmatic Embodiment of Social Sciences

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INTRODUCTION:

There are four key aspects that Data Scientist can use as key milestones. These are "Narrative, Ethnography, Phenomenology and Grounded Theory". Each and every part of a problem, that Data Scientists look into can have potential four paths. These constitute, "Descriptive, Predictive, Prescriptive and Decision" Analytical approaches. All analytical needs must be broken down from the "Narrative to Grounded Theory". This creates an ease of attribute selection for the application of Factor Analysis, application of Regression and Correlation to find strong or weak relationships.

AIM:

The elaboration of effective utilization of Social Sciences within the domain of Big Data and Data Science.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The initiation of projects relate to Big Data & Data Science need a Social perspective coverage. This can be achieved by the application of Social Sciences, such as the use of Narrative, Ethnography, Phenomenology and Grounded Theory Implementation before we as Data Scientists/Big Data Architects have a deep dive in applying Machine learning algorithms.

RESULTS:

This is a discussion on the Social Sciences embodiment within the domain of the Data Science.

CONCLUSIONS:

Unless we know the Narrative of stakeholders, who are willing to make some decisions, however at their hands have Big Data in a Data Lake.

KEYWORDS:

Big Data, Data Science, Social Science, Machine Learning

BIOGRAPHY:

Atif has a doctorate in Information Technology, and is a Professor of Computer/Data Science as well as a Senior level Big Data Architect and Data Science Evangelist with diversified experience as individual Software Engineering and Big Data SME experience in the areas of traditional and non-traditional technology stacks, such as Database Management Systems, Threat Intelligence, Big Data and Data Science. Atif has more than twenty (20) years experience of

technology integration. Atif's 10 year goal from 2013 to 2023 is to become a Level 5 Leader to lead by example.